

THE ECONOMIC IMPACT OF TRANSYLVANIAN EVOLUTION IN 1867-1914

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Abstract :

The paper postulates the importance of the economic impact of the Transylvanian Saxons migration on Romanian interest. Through the paper are identified the economic reasons, causes and factors that led the development of the Romanian society of the 1867 – 1914 Transylvanian Saxons migration. In the same time, the research, an exploratory one, presents the economic impact of Saxons guilds in 1867-1914 period. Transylvanian entrepreneurial values are highlighted through organizational and ethical benches of the Saxons, too. In the capitalist sense, the economic development of Transylvania after 1867 was stimulated by commerce and investments. The Austro-Hungarian economic rules has accomplished in different areas of Transylvania and Banat. Transylvanian economy took advantage of high rates in developing the Austro-Hungarian economy, especially with the inflows of capital invested in roads, railways and industrial training modernization. By 1880, Austro-Hungarian Empire promoted a liberal economic policy, encouraging massive exports and eliminating the obstacles that stood in the way of developing a competitive economy. All these sustained the Transylvania and Banat areas, propagandize the Saxons well-being over the mountains into the other part of the Romanian Kingdom. Overall, the entrepreneurship of the Transylvanian Saxons developed social and physical roots for the Romanian regions.

Key-words: *dualism, migration, Austro-Hungary, economy, economic politics, Transylvanian Saxons*

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Up until the second half of the sixteenth century, Transylvania was integrated in the political and administrative system of the Hungarian Kingdom. The princely institution and the ethnic and confessional pluralism undoubtedly offer proof of a local particularism, yet, like everywhere in the era, the allegiance to the Crown has to be judged by the servants, not by their ethnicity or confession [1].

For Hungary, the temporary dynastic union with Poland (1370-1382) and the implication of royalty in the imperial political system, during the rule of Louis of Anjou and Sigismund of Luxembourg, meant the peak of its continental power [2].

This followed after the midst of the fifteenth century, a stationary period, marked by the amplification of internal strife. The royalty proved unsuccessful in constructing a system that was centralized, hierarchical and loyal to the state. Incapable of keeping the situation under control, the monarch remained as simply the bearer of The Crown of Saint Stefan, which, *de jure*, was in the successor sphere of the Imperial Court, while, *de facto*, it was just an attribute granted during the life of the Hungarian king. The Treaties of Sopron (Oedenburg, 1463) and Pozsony (Pressburg, 1491) are practical proof of this.

Until the middle of the seventeenth century, the Principality's main focus was the mutations which occurred during the evolution of international relations in the continent's central and south-eastern parts. Mostly, the efforts of combating the House of Austria have continued through the Principe's function of guarantors and defenders of the political and spiritual values of the Hungarians within the Kingdom, often aided by the deceiving actions of Ottoman dignitaries. During the Rákoczi dynasty, politically, the Kingdom's goals were the implication of Sweden and Romanian states in the quest for personal goals, such as obtaining the Polish Crown and triggering a war against the Ottoman. This led to the reestablishment of authority over Transylvania through radical measures, meant to stop a riot which would have affected its points of interest in the area. The organization of Oradea's vilayet, the strict supervising of the Principality meant to stop Austrian interference and also, the cancellation of juridical support for its own political value, based on the dynastic principle, have had grave repercussions for the juridical status of the country.

In the second half of the seventeenth century, Transylvania was engaged in developing the military force ratio between Austria and The High Gate. The military abandon which took place under the walls of Vienna, in 1683, and the Turks' inability to stop the advance of imperial troops towards the intra-Carpathian space, have forced The Gate to accept the treaty of Karlowitz (1699). This act approved to the most important loss of territories suffered by The Gate in Europe. Austria won the international acknowledgement of these changes only with the treaty of Rástadt (1714).

Economic relations between Romanians and the Saxons, starting with the ending of the fourteenth century and ending with the middle of the sixteenth century, of over a century and a half, have, mostly, different characteristics from those in past and the future [3].

Economic relations in the above-mentioned period, and not just the ones between Romanians and Saxons, bear the marks of a period of flourish for the feudal system. This is available both at the level and functionality of Romanian economy and at the Saxons' contribution to the general development of Romanian economy.

Romanian chroniclers have in their writings little aspects of the socio-economical life of Saxons [4]. The Saxon chroniclers offer special attention to the commercial ties among Transylvania, Moldavia and the Romanian Country, the Saxon's trade with the two extra Carpathian countries, placing it as the top spot of Saxon trader activity. Some writings, however, contain not only economic data, but also certain aspects of day-to-day life and the harsh situation of the Romanians under Turk dominion [5].

It is worth mentioning that economic and social relations are tied in closely to political ones, some improving, or, sometimes, degrading the others. The Saxons knew how to profit of these circumstances, obtaining privileges for their trade [6].

In its external relations, the Principality of Transylvania, which lasted a century and a half, evolved between the two biggest powers facing off in south-eastern Europe. In this era, the relations between Romanians and Saxons have continued to manifest themselves on several levels. They have been influenced by two factors. Firstly, because of the foreign dominion, the large taxes demanded by The Gate, important amounts of money and cargo went towards Constantinople; the economic relations were, therefore, mostly regulated. On the other hand, regarding the relations between Romanians and Saxons, those were forced not to interfere with the Turks' points of interest, although this happened on several occasions, during fights against the Ottoman dominion [7].

The Austro-Hungarian dualism, materialized through the pact in 1867 between the dominant Austrian and Hungarian classes, has roots standing long before the pact of 1867, being able to be found from the first dozens of years of Habsburgic dominion over Transylvania and systematically traced up to 1867, with a permanent tendency of political compromise from the Hungarian ruling class and the Austrian Habsburgic monarchy.

In spite of the conflicts between Austrian and Hungarian politicians, those have resolved and removed their contradictions, with the purpose of defending each other against non-German and non-Hungarian ethnicities which wanted to destroy the Austrian and Hungarian state centralism, in order to ethnically federalize the monarchy with autonomous national states.

The dualist system, instated in 1867, with the Twelfth Law, brought back the Hungarian national governing and reestablished the Hungarian supremacy over Romanians and Slavs, in the forms of 1848.

In a moment in which beneficial effects for Romanians were expected, in conformity with the principles of liberalism (1860-1865), this favorable course of events was brutally stopped, as consequence of Vienna's switch from secret treaties, to public political actions, in the spring of 1865, in order to improve relations with the Hungarian aristocracy and bourgeoisie [8]. As consequence of the movements of different nationalities in the Habsburgic Empire, internal difficulties appeared. The most important difficulties were the ones of the Hungarians and, externally, the defeat in the war against Prussia. These difficulties have made The House of Habsburg accept the collaborative insistence of the Hungarian aristocracy and bourgeoisie and also, the "sine qua non" condition supported by the Hungarians from even before the start of the negotiations for treaties.

For the Saxon community, the time before the First World War was one of major changes, especially political ones. But these also affected areas like economy and social aspects. Once the absolutism installed, the constitutions meant to organize Saxons' lives were canceled, and University had to close. It seemed that the sober general atmosphere influenced Saxons' attitude towards the spread of the nation. Reissenberger mentions several factors that could have determined this evolution [9]. The most important one takes into consideration the economic aspects. The crafting production and the commerce suffered indeed during post-revolutionary years, affecting the financial comfort of a large number of Saxons. After the first measures of reducing guilds' activities, the first ones affected by the competition of imported industrial products were the wavers. Reissenberger' thesis states that a certain social layer is most affected by the negative effects of a financial crisis if this is situated on a higher level. Anyway, if we were to think about Saxons, they were the most well off from the entire Transylvanian ethnic mosaic. It is only obvious that they suffered the most due to the events marking the mid sixth century. We are talking, of course, of Crimean War and its counterpart, a more expensive life [10].

Both the Forty-Eighters Revolution and the Crimean War led to the loss, at least temporary, of important sales markets for commerce products and Saxon crafting production, which had as main target the Principalities and Turkey. The disaster produced by floods in 1851, the constant increasing taxes, the costs generated by troops presence in Transylvania, in brief, a more expensive life, had double consequences. On one side, these aspects determined a higher exposure of that particular segment of Saxon population to pathogenic agents, because they were unable to efficiently manage the economic resources. On the other side, the economic tension has combined with a feeling of insecurity, generated by state politics, due to the new post-revolutionary general orientation and the countless administrative changes, and by the social comfort threatened by the state of war from a nearby geographic location [11].

The period between 1869 and 1880 was marked by several disease breakouts, others than cholera. The economic field was also often affected by the lack of aliments.

Regarding Saxons, they started by being an autonomous nation since colonization and ended up becoming an ethnic minority; their economy, based on the caste system of guilds, suffered major transformations and had to adapt to a more and more difficult market [12].

Even if in 1867, Austro-Hungary had an agricultural prevalent economy, with a weak industry, the following factors encouraged the development and the economic growth of the empire economic powers, during 1867-1884: economic politics, promoted after 1867, the significant growth of intern market, and the economic conjuncture favorable on an international level. This development was interrupted only by the economic crisis in 1872-1873.

In this context, the economic growth of Transylvania after 1867, regarded from a capitalistic point of view, was also encouraged by the investment made by the Austro-Hungarian state in different areas of Transylvania and Banat. Transylvania's economy took advantage of the high rates of development from the Austro-Hungarian Empire (especially of that from Hungary), of the incoming invested capital, of the road modernization, of the rail network and industrial system. Till the '80s, Austro-Hungary promoted a liberal economic

politics, encouraging massive exports and eliminating any obstacle in its way to a developed competitive economy [13].

Capitalism growth affected Transylvania agriculture too, after 1867. The economic conjuncture favorable on an intern and international level for agricultural products was interrupted by the economic crisis in 1872-1873 and restarted in the '80s. This one determined a considerable growth of the agricultural ground surface. Thus, in 1867, the ground surface dedicated to agriculture was of about 17.3 million ha, in 1869, the arable areas reached almost 2.8 million ha, and in 1895 ended up covering 3.3 million ha. Starting with the second half of the nineteenth century, in Transylvania, the triennial cultivation system became a general rule, people having a tendency towards intensive exploitation of earth. Till the economic crisis in 1872-1873, Transylvanian agriculture was dominated by cereals. This aspect was encouraged by the integration of agricultural exploitation in the market economy, by the establishment of the huge Austro-Hungarian Empire market, by the fast industrialization, by the construction and the development of railway network.

The demographic growth and the industrial revolution determined an increasing demand for wood and wooden products. Therefore, in the second half of the nineteenth century, the timber industry gained great momentum and a forest economics started to take shape as an independent economic sector. In this period, wood industry progressed from technical points of view, too. Still, the abusive exploitation of forests contributed to the degradation of forestry areas and to the deforestation of large agricultural surfaces.

The development, growth and modernization of Transylvanian industry, after 1867, were supported by the state. The rivalry represented by the Austro-Hungarian products and the economic traditional ties determined Transylvania to look for industrial and commercial markets in Romania. This was possible because the state encouraged exports through commercial signed agreements.

In this context, Saxons developed the concept of double loyalty which characterized their relationships with other nations, their political and spiritual position in the following years: on one side, they acknowledged the German influence, even overreacting in this regard; on the other side, they acknowledged the state they were living in and its leadership, even if this was more and more criticized.

It is well-known that Hungary, as well as the other half of the Austro-Hungarian Monarchy, was one of the most heterogeneous European countries, as regarding nationalities and confessions, till the first global conflagration. Experts are quasi-unanimous when it comes to agreeing that between 1850 and 1910, considerable ethnic and linguistic changes took place in monarchy. In these conditions, we will notice that, between the two temporal limits, in Transylvania took place ethnical and linguistic changes, differing in amplitude, based on the dynamic of the population, emigration and the authorities' scholar economic and cultural policy [14].

The first post-revolution census, the one in 1850-1851, noted the unchallenged majority of Romanians in historical Transylvania (Ardeal) (59,5%). The changes suffered by the three principal ethnicities of Transylvania during the dualism are as follows: Romanians have regressed to 54,9% in 1800, to 53,7% in 1910, the Germans regressed as well, to 12% in 1880,

but, on the other hand, the Hungarian have grown in number, from 25,2, to 31,6%. The causes of this growth are varied, but, the most commonly used ones are the natural increase of the Hungarian ethnicity, the low number of emigrants from this ethnicity and “in a small measure” the ethnical and linguistic assimilation of Jews, Armenians and a few thousands of Czechs, Poles and Italians arrived on those lands in “the vortex of industrialization.”

A. of Gerando, a foreign traveler in the nineteenth century, observed the phenomenon of “Szekelyzation” of the Romanian ethnic element in the area: “Today, there are more Szecklers with the Greek religion. All of those are denationalized Wallachians.” [15]. The Orthodox and Greek-Catholic confessions were, as of 1850, at 15.4% and, as of 1910, at 17.3%. As such, we observe that, in 1850, there was a difference of 5.8% between the average of Romanians and the two confessions. [16]. The assimilation of Romanians in the area happened spontaneously, naturally, through mixed weddings, but after 1867, the process was clearly directed by authorities, as a consequence of the Hungarian demographic policies. A way the authorities of Budapest tried to influence the ethnical composition of Transylvania, in the latter half of the nineteenth century and the beginning of the twentieth century, are the colonies of Hungarian peasants, or foreign populations made in different parts of the province. These colonies had a real economic purpose, but, undeniably, they were made with political intent.

At the census of 1870, the population of Transylvania, Banat, Crisana and Maramures was of 4.224.614 citizens, with a density of 41 people per square kilometer. In the former Principality of Transylvania’s lands, the population was of 2.393.000 citizens, with a density of 39.4 per square kilometer, this being a growth of 15.4% from 1850 and 10.1% from 1897. On the territory of the former principality were, in 1870, 2.799 stable settlements, 33 of which were considered cities (31 free kingly cities and 2 council cities), 54 markets, 2.609 villages and 103 hamlets.

The growth in the Principality’s population between 1857 and 1869, with 10.1% is specific to the demographical regime in Central Europe, being close to the one in Hungary (9.4%) and Croatia (10.1%).

This demographic growth was the consequence of economic and social mutations of the Transylvanian society, of the abolishment of feudal servitude, and the allotment of the former bondsmen. At the following census, the one of 1880, in Transylvania, Banat, Crisana and Maramures, was registered a population of 4.081.662 citizens, with a density of 39.7 p/km². Compared to 1870, there was a loss of 142.952 (3.4%) with an annual decrease average of 0.3%. In the former Great Principality, the population amounted to 2.225.127 citizens, with a density of 37.9% p/km², the population decreasing with 138.079 citizens (5.8%) with an annual lowering average of -0.53%, compared to 1870.

At the time of this census, in the Principality were 2.631 stable settlements, 32 of which were cities (2 free kingly cities and 30 cities with a council), 2.599 villages and 458.261 houses. The demographic decline of the province was the result of the devastating cholera epidemic between 1872 and 1873, which claimed 22.053 victims of local smallpox, diphtheria and convulsive coughing epidemics from 1871, 1874, 1876 and 1879, with effects affecting the children in special. The economic crises in 1872-1873 and the following years of drought and weak harvests added to this. Demographical behavior in this period has the same characteristics

as those of the old regime. The brute rate of natural surplus had the following evolution: 1856-1859: 11.8%, 1866-1870: 8.1%, 1871-1875: 5.7%, 1876-1880: 4.4%.

The phenomenon of permanent emigration toward Romania will emphasize only after 1880. The censuses of 1850 and 1857 have noted the absence of 30.731 citizens, 54.566 of which in the former Great Principality, most of which, gone to work in Romania, but those ones were temporary migrations, allowed by agricultural tasks. In 1863, from Transylvania to Romania, a number of 62.827 people, in 1864, 57.941 people and in 1865, 67.623 people have gone. From the eighties, the handicraftsmen and agriculturalists which occasionally went to Romania were from the southern areas of Transylvania, especially from the Szekler communities. Between 1870 and 1880, the biggest migrating increase was registered, over 130.000 people, the natural increase being only 5.079, which meant that about 130.000 people left the province.

An important mark of the modernization process of Transylvania was the ratio of urban to rural population, in the second half of the nineteenth century. At the start of this period, urbanization in Transylvania was in the central and south-western pattern, which is characterized through the existence of many urban or semi urban settlements, with a population between 2.000 and 5.000 residents, with a very small amount of cities with over 10.000 residents.

The growth of urban population was the result of intern migration of the rural population excess towards cities. This process started at the same time with the industrialization one, and didn't manifest through natural increase in population, but through the absorption of population excess from nearby villages. The growth of urban population didn't evolve regularly. The growth rhythm of urban population was superior to that of the rural population growth. Thus, between 1850 and 1857, urban population increased with 41%, and between 1857 and 1869, with 14,6%. In the same period, the growth of rural population was of 9,9% and decreased between 1870 and 1880.

The ethnic and confessional structure of the former Great Transylvanian Principality had a contradictory evolution, because there was no concordance between the percentage of Romanian ethnicity population and the Romanian confessions. It is worth mentioning that the censuses during the dualist period didn't record people's nationality, but only the mother tongue. This happened between 1867 and 1884, and was interrupted by the economic crisis in 1872-1873.

Human society had and has as a basis multiple forms of community which allow the forming of complex relationships among people. One of these forms of community is the family and it has the quality of being one of the oldest of such systems. Family has countless roles and its members are united not only by the same lineage, but also by interests and goals. In these conditions, in time, society has regarded family and its role as being very important. The next step was implementing the rules allowing the formation of such matrimonial ties, stronger than other relationships imposed by community. Then, the state and the Church fought over the rights regarding the family institution and aspects like marriage and its annulment, children's raise and education, money gaining and administration [17].

In the paper dedicated to ecclesiastic Romanian writings in Transylvania, from the second half of the nineteenth century, Corina Teodor stated that the period between 1850 and 1870 can be characterized by the legitimizing historiography, while between 1870 and 1910 the confessionalized historiography dominated [18].

The defeat of Forty-Eighters revolution from the Austrian Empire led to the establishment of a new absolutist regime that had as main preoccupations the centralization and consolidation of loyalty.

Church was among the institutions serving the Empire. Catholic Church was privileged due to the special relationship between the House of Habsburg emperors and The Holy See that had a fervent supporter in the second half of the nineteenth century: Emperor Franz Joseph. Because of this imperial availability, the setback of Iosefinism took place by the annulment of measures keeping the Austrian state away from The Holy See. In these conditions, the direct connections between papal administration and Catholic Church jurisdictions from the Austrian Empire were marked by the need of local realities reinstatement, reorganization and misconduct corrections, occurred in the decades following Joseph II [19].

With the same purpose of getting closer to The Holy See politics, the United Metropolitan Church of Fagaras and Alba Iulia was restored in 1853 [20].

In this period of major changes for all Romanians from provinces under foreign rule, especially political changes, it seems that Romanians from Transylvania defended the best their national identity. They were aware of the nation's historical rights in Transylvania and had a long past period of common fight that helped them stay united. Additionally, they benefited from two powerful national institutions – Orthodox and Greek Catholic Churches, with headquarters in Sibiu and Blaj; also, starting with the second half of the nineteenth century, Transylvania had tight connections with politicians from Romanian Kingdom.

In the last decades of nineteenth century, till the beginning of the First World War, Romanians' dynamics in Transylvania was led by a middle class of reduced, but growing size. This was made out of business people and Greek Catholics as national leaders. Their main objective was political autonomy and self-determination. These hopes were crushed by the suppression of revolution in 1848 and the imposition of a centralized regime in the following decade. However, the idea of autonomy represented the cohesion force among political Romanian organizations. At the beginning of '60s, this ideal seemed to be finally achieved, because the Court of Vienna was seeking Romanians' and Slaves' help in order to counteract Hungarians' aspirations and experiment new constitutional forms. In Transylvania, the Court of Vienna allowed Diet convocation with a large number of Romanian representatives, and adopted a legislation that acknowledged the political equality of Romanians and other populations from Transylvania, and granted an official statute to Romanian language, along with Hungarian and German. Most of Romanian leaders hesitated to interfere in the fundamental political structures. They were sure that the autonomous Transylvania was offering an indispensable constitutional framework where the new national equality could have been transformed into a national autonomy [21].

All these facts prove that the dualist Austro-Hungarian pact made in 1867 was the result of a constitutional arrangement, meant to strengthen the Habsburg Empire. Through this pact,

the Hungarian political class was given leadership rights by the Austrian one, that ensured a substantial increased role of Hungarian ethnic role in state.

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